

An Exploratory Study into Perceptions of Grade 11 Learners towards School-Based Sex Education

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Abstract:- The qualitative study aimed to explore the perceptions of Grade 11 learners towards school-based sex education in Randburg, Johannesburg. A phenomenological design was used and a sample of 5 male and 5 female Grade 11 learners was obtained through snowball sampling. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. Findings of the study indicated that while learners believed that sex education in schools was appropriate, it was shallow and needed a more in-depth approach. Learners believed that emotional issues regarding sexual activity needed to be discussed and that LGBTQIA youth should be catered for. 5 recommendations were identified and included an open, honest learning environment; in-depth classes as well as a learner-focused approach to sex education.

Keywords:- Sex, school based sex education, LGBTQIA, schools, sexuality.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sexuality education and research are imperative to young people learning and understanding sexuality (Fields & Tolman, 2006). Schools remain a place where many young people spend majority of their time and so schools have become one of the best places to reach a broad and diverse community of students. School-based sex education legitimizes and recognises sexuality as part of a young person's life, regardless of how they are negotiating the

challenges and promises associated with their sexuality (Fields & Tolman, 2006). The referent adolescent sexual health programs have been a way of combating medical, emotional and physical threats to the well-being of adolescents for a long time and hence, schools have become effective tools used to manage the sexuality of children in an attempt to reduce unwanted consequences such as; teenage pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections (STI's) (McCarty-Caplan, 2013).

The introduction and existence, or lack thereof sex education has been miscellaneously ascribed to increasing rates of teenage pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases among young people. However, sex education remains a contested issue as there are still anxiety, fears and stigma associated around the discussion about sex and sexuality (Buston, Scott & Wight, 2001). However, Fields & Tolman (2006) assert that 'both research and education also reflect a commitment to learning more about youth and sexuality on many levels, not only about their risk for HIV, sexually transmitted diseases (STD's), and pregnancy, but also about their feelings, perceptions, and needs - including the nature of desire, stigma, agency, identity, and the human right to ask and know about oneself' (p.64).

Sex education is fundamentally comprised of three elements (Buston Scott & Wight, 2001) which form the ABC model of attitude as shown in figure 1 (Jain, 2014).

Fig. 1: ABC Model of Attitude (Jain, 2014)

As shown above, these elements are the cognitive, the affective and the behavioural. The cognitive element is related to beliefs, knowledge and perceptions and includes the facts and information about sex education specified to the students. The affective element relates to feelings, emotions and preferences and includes the attitudes and values of students related to sex. Lastly the behavioural aspect includes actions and intentions and thereby attempts to ensure that students have grasped and understood the material and are able to effectively communicate and make responsible decisions with regards to sex (Buston, Scott & Wight, 2001; Jain, 2014).

Sex education was developed to navigate inconsistent fears of sexualised adolescents - with a focus on making young people strict adherents of the established code of sexual morality. It was not developed to create new sexual ideals through abstinence only education. Despite this intention, sex education was initially met with opposition. There was public outcry against discussing sex in a classroom setting. Critics and conservatives argued that even if the intentions were beneficent, any open discussion with adolescents about sex and sexuality would inevitably lead to the pollution of young minds and social degradation; thereby launching campaigns aimed at denouncing premarital sex, homosexuality, liberal sex education and abortion (McCarty-Caplan, 2013).

Abstinence-only education, however, does not reflect the reality of adolescent sexual behaviour. It is often scientifically incorrect and does not effectively reduce adolescent sexual health risk but may rather perpetuate these risks by providing misleading, inaccurate or stigmatizing information (McCarty-Caplan, 2013). Frustration with abstinence-only education paved the way for a more comprehensive approach to sex education, which is referred to as comprehensive sex education.

McCarty-Caplan (2013) state that comprehensive sex education may be defined as “sex education that not only teaches abstinence as the best method for avoiding STD’s and unintended pregnancy but also teaches about the benefits of risk-reduction such as condom and contraception use. Additionally, comprehensive sex education includes education on interpersonal and communication skills, and helps young people explore their own values, goals and options” (p.252).

Comprehensive sex education that includes a more liberal discussion of contraceptives, premarital sexual activity and sexuality is in line with realistic adolescent sexual behaviour and provides more medically accurate information (McCarty-Caplan, 2013). When young people are allowed to assert themselves in dialogue about and reflections on their sexuality, they force educators to respond to subjectivity that adults who typically make decisions about students’ lives in school often avoid (Fields & Tolman, 2006).

A. Aim

The study aims to evaluate Grade 11 learners’ perceptions towards school based sex education (SBSE). In doing so, it will allow policy makers and schools to understand learners’ views around what they believe sex education entails, and should include.

B. Objectives

The study aimed to determine the perceptions of Grade 11 learners towards school-based sex education in the Randburg area of Johannesburg, South Africa. The specific objectives of this study were:

- To ascertain learners’ understanding of sex education
- To determine what content learners would like to be included in sex education programs.
- To identify how learners evaluate sex education currently being taught.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Population

The target population for this study consisted of 5 male and 5 female grade 11 learners who have been exposed to school based sex education and who reside in the Randburg area of Johannesburg.

B. Sampling and sampling techniques

This study used non-probability methods in the form of snowballing sampling which resulted in a sample of ten participants – five female and five male Grade 11 learners of various races (Black, White, Coloured and Indian) who live in the Randburg area and attend different public schools.

C. Data gathering instruments

The study used in depth interviews to collect data. This method allowed for the comprehension of the underlying phenomena by using open-ended questions to understand the perceptions, attitudes, opinions and feelings of the learners and enhanced the exploratory nature of the study. A structured interview schedule was used to keep structure and guide participants. The participants were allowed and encouraged to elaborate on their answers as the questions were open-ended. The interviews were conducted telephonically. Telephonic interviews were used in this study as they were deemed to be the most efficient way to complete the interviews in a timely manner and in a way that was convenient to the learners.

D. Procedure

The study made use of telephonic interviews of 5 males and 5 females. Consent forms were emailed to participants beforehand and the interviews commenced only after consent forms, signed by both the parent and the participant, were returned. As previously mentioned, the interviews used a structured interview schedule and questions were sent to participants. Participants were given the option to send individually typed responses, one continuous typed response or a recorded response via voice notes over the WhatsApp social media platform. The interviewer sought clarity and added follow up questions where necessary.

E. Design

This study was guided by the phenomenological paradigm. Groenewald (2004) describes phenomenology as being concerned with understanding psychological and social events from the perspectives of the individuals involved. The advantages of using a phenomenological approach is that it acquires unique perspectives from participants, that is, it allows the researcher to focus on the ways in which individuals perceive a phenomenon rather than the way it exists in a vacuum. The phenomenological approach was used as it provides an understanding and description of participants' experiences of a phenomenon, which in this case were the perceptions towards school based sex education.

F. Data analysis

Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data obtained. Miles & Huberman (1994) identified a model for the thematic analysis process which consists of three stages that focus on visualising data through display techniques such as quotations and figures; organising research concepts and building coherent findings.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results revealed that learners feel that overall, the content in school-based sex education programs is not effectively catering to their needs. Some learners believe that although many topics are being covered, they are being taught in a way that only scratches the surface and does not provide enough information that will address the learners' questions and needs. Other learners believe that only negative aspects are being taught while neglecting to include emotional topics and topics on consent.

A. Understanding of sex education

Guided by the research topic, it was important to understand the learners' ideas and understanding of sex education. Although answers to this question varied, mostly all focused on the aspects related to the content and aims of sex education.

While most of the responses echoed similar responses, one contrasting response stood out, *"I don't have an understanding of sex education, I come from an Indian family that doesn't talk about it at all."*

From the responses given, it becomes clear that there is not one universal definition that may be used to describe sex education and that understanding is subjective and varies from one individual to another. However, common general themes that can be derived from the definitions given by learners are that sex education includes sexuality, prevention of sex-related diseases and contraception.

B. Does Sex Education Belong in Schools?

This section illustrates the belief that majority of learners believe that sex education has a place in schools. Reasons for this belief ranged from an inability to discuss sexual issues at home due to it still being considered taboo, to being an additional source of reliable information that is not informed by peers, peer pressure and the internet. While majority of the learners interviewed were in agreement that sex education has

a place in schools, one learner was strongly opposed to the idea that sex education should be taught in schools

C. Other Sources of Sex Education Compared to School Based Sex Education

It is evident that the internet is the most widely used alternative to school-based sex education, where majority of learners stated they are learning about sex via YouTube and pornography. While exploring this theme it emerged that some learners, sought out information because they believed that school-based education was too formal and that it was difficult to open up during sexual education lessons for various reasons that included, shyness and fear of being negatively labelled. With one student stating *"...None really, it's usually just my friends and then I have to Google some stuff just to make sure. School based education is more formal and we don't always get to be free and ask and understand some stuff. Some people are shy and will never say anything in front of the class or because they're scared of being judged as being stuck up or a hoe...The boys can be a bit silly and immature about it as well sometimes."*

D. Topics Learners Would Like to be Included

This theme dealt with topics learners would want to be included in sex education programmes. It was clear from the responses that while learners had been presented with topics discussing the physical aspects of sex; such as STI's and the use of contraceptives, emotional aspects had been neglected. It also emerged that the female students believed that not enough time was spent discussing all the options females had with regards to contraception as well as female masturbation.

E. Inclusivity of All Gender Groups and Sexual Orientations

The beliefs and perceptions communicated within this theme are indicative of the fact that despite slight differences in the reasons why, all participants were unanimous in their views that school-based sex education should be inclusive of the LGBTQIA community. Participants felt that currently sex education curriculums do not cater to this community adding to the stigmatisation and misunderstanding of these minority groups. Further, participants believe that LGBTQIA individuals may have a need for a more specialised curriculum that focuses on the ways in which gay and lesbian groups engage in sexual intercourse, anal sex and the use of lubricants which is not currently addressed, with statements from a student including *"Yes, I think it should. Why do I say it should include all gender groups? Because everyone can get an STD, whether you are gay or straight or lesbian. And also, people have identity crisis...some people they don't even know if they are gay or straight, they don't even know how to have sex and using lubricants and those type of things and also how to have sex properly without dire consequences."*

F. Evaluation of sex education content

How school-based sex education is evaluated is a central theme and focus of this study. Analysis of the responses given to the question, "How would you evaluate the content being taught?", shows another case where all participants unanimously agree that content currently being taught in SBSE programs is sub-par at best and leaves room for improvement.

IV. CONCLUSION

The motivating force behind conducting this exploratory study arose from literature that suggests that adolescents views tend to be excluded from implementation of SBSE programs, and the belief that a learner centred approach was the key to unlocking the full potential of SBSE programs by engaging with the youth and including content and information that learners actually want to know.

The study revealed that learners believe that sex education has a place in schools as it offers them a place to learn about sex that has adult perspective and oversight. The need for school based sex education is noted in Kapinga & Hyera's (2015) study on student perceptions on sex education in Tanzania. They found that education is important to learners over the age of 10 years old.

Learners believe that issues of sex are uncomfortable and awkward to discuss with parents. However, they did not only want to rely on their peers and the internet for sex as the information provided had a higher chance of being inaccurate and so school provided a type of balance in learning for them. Although they (the learners) believed that sex education belonged in school, the identified certain problems in the way that it was being taught. Goldman (2005) found that it was imperative for schools to provide children with an authentic and satisfying learning environment. She further adds that school based sexuality is extremely relevant and universally applicable.

The study concluded that much can be learned from studying adolescents perceptions and experiences if adolescents are given an opportunity and platform to express their views, with a learner centred approach making it easier for learners to internalise the information and messages provided, resulting in lasting behaviour change or modifications and effectively reducing problems associated with sexual risk-taking behaviours and consequences.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings of this study, the following policy recommendations have been made:

Policy makers and schools should not view students as passive in the learning process and provide learners with opportunities to express their views in order to implement programs that address learners needs.

Policy makers and schools should provide full accurate and in-depth information to students regarding all aspects of sex, sexuality and all contraceptive options available to them. In doing so, learners will be given the ability to make informed, responsible decisions about their sexual health.

An open, honest and non-judgemental environment needs to be cultivated in schools in order for students to open up about issues affecting them and to seek clarification on issues they are unsure about.

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